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Mesenchymal Stem Cell Therapy from Bone Marrow and Associated Orthobiologic Treatments

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Abstract

The current article's goal is to examine the body of research on the use of bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cell treatment to treat musculoskeletal disorders and to highlight the urgent need for more carefully planned clinical trials. Mesenchymal stem cells generated from bone marrow have garnered significant attention in the treatment of musculoskeletal disorders and injuries in recent years. The clinical application of BM-MSCs and other stem cell therapies has progressed well beyond the basic and translational research data needed to clarify the possible effectiveness of this orthobiologic therapeutic strategy. Mesenchymal stem cell therapy derived from bone marrow has shown promise in treating knee osteoarthritis, focal chondral lesions, shoulder pathologies such as glenohumeral arthritis, rotator cuff tears, and degenerative disk disease in the spine. These findings are consistent with early research findings. The majority of research that has been published to date are brief case series that frequently don't have a control group or a set course of therapy. Mesenchymal stem cell therapy produced from bone marrow is becoming a more popular treatment for diseases and accidents related to the musculoskeletal system. Despite encouraging results from early clinical trials, methodological errors and a lack of trial standardization have restricted the inferences that can be made from the body of current research. The effectiveness and usefulness of BM-MSCs as a therapy option for different orthopedic disorders will become clearer with a deeper comprehension of the underlying mechanism of action and more meticulously planned clinical trials.

Keywords: Stem cell, Regenerative medicine, Mesenchymal stem cell

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Introduction

Arnold Caplan and others reported their findings on the extraction of mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) from bone marrow and the capacity of MSCs to develop into bone and cartilage under particular in vitro settings in the late 1980s (1). Clinical research examining the potential therapeutic uses of stem cell therapy and regenerative medicine has rapidly increased since the discovery of MSCs. There has been particular interest in the potential clinical applications for musculoskeletal injury and disease because of early in vitro studies showing that bone marrow-derived MSCs (BM-MSCs) can be purified, culture-expanded, and induced to differentiate into mesodermal tissue types (2).

However, the clinical application of BM-MSCs and other stem cell therapies has advanced far faster than the fundamental and translational research needed to clarify their possible benefits. Patients are routinely given a range of bone marrow-derived cell and tissue preparations with unverified promises of positive results and therapeutic potential [5]. Because of this, the Federal Trade Commission has started to prosecute stem cell therapy clinics that have been found to have broken truth-in-advertising regulations (3).

When BM-MSCs are employed for osteoarthritis and localized chondral defects, early clinical investigations have demonstrated promising results, despite the unethical activities of clinics capitalizing on the excitement of regenerative medicine. However, we still have a limited grasp of these preparations of cells and tissues. There are methodological shortcomings in the research that contribute to the difficulty of making firm claims about the effectiveness of BM-MSCs in treating orthopedic disorders. Therefore, the current article's goal is to analyze the body of research on bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cell therapy and argue that more carefully planned clinical trials are necessary (4).

The International Society for Cellular Therapy (ISCT) established strict requirements that cells need to fulfill to be classified as MSCs in 2006. In addition to exhibiting particular surface antigens and demonstrating in vitro differentiation into osteoblasts, adipocytes, and chondroblasts, the cells must be plastic-adherent in conventional culture conditions (5). Yet, since this class of cells was first characterized, the definition of "MSC" has changed multiple times. As our knowledge of these cells' characteristics has grown, many groups that disagree on the most appropriate term for the cell type have described "MSC" as mesenchymal stem cell, mesodermal stem cell, and mesenchymal stromal cell, frequently simultaneously (6).

At first, it was believed that MSCs would retain their multipotency after being injected into a damaged joint because of their capacity to go through in vitro osteogenesis and chondrogenesis. For this reason, the ability of mesenchymal stem cells to specialize and restore injured soft tissue or cartilage was postulated. Subsequent research, however, showed that MSCs originate from pericytes or the perivascular cells that envelop the capillary endothelium. According to studies, injected MSCs do not differentiate in vivo and do not serve as stem cells in their primary capacity (7).

Regulatory Aspects to Be Considered in Orthobiologics

The FDA's Public Health Service (PHS) Act governs the use of human cells, tissues, and cellular and tissue-based products (HCT/Ps), which include bone marrow-derived tissue preparations that are both autologous and allogeneic. Two major types of tissue preparations that are meant to be injected or infused into a human recipient are defined by the PHS Act. For HCT/Ps meant for homologous use and with minimum manipulation, Section 361 of the PHS Act is applicable. The FDA states that the processing method for tissues or cells that have undergone minimal manipulation cannot "alter relevant biological characteristics of cells or tissue" or "alter the original relevant characteristics relating to the tissue's utility for reconstruction, repair, and replacement". "The repair, reconstruction, replacement, or supplementation of a recipient's cells or tissues with an HCT/P that performs the same basic function or functions in the recipient as in the donor" is what is referred to as homologous usage. Furthermore, Section 361 stipulates that the cells may only be mixed with "water, crystalloids, or a sterilizing,

preserving, or storage agent" in place of any other tissue or product (8). FDA premarket approval is not required for the administration of cell and tissue preparations to patients if they fulfill the requirements outlined in Section 361.

Section 351 of the PHS Act governs HCT/Ps that are more than slightly modified, meant for non-homologous usage, or mixed with another tissue-based product. For bone marrow-derived cells, homologous usage entails "forming and replenishing the lymphohematopoietic system," per the FDA. Moreover, MSC culture growth is defined as including more than minimal modification. Except for transplants given to a donor's first- or second-degree relatives, allogeneic HCT/Ps are inherently exempt from PHS Act Section 361 regulations. Consequently, most BM-MSCs preparations that have been employed in clinical studies fall under Section 351 regulation since they do not satisfy the requirements for Section 361 goods. Products covered by Section 351 must submit a completed Biologic License Application to the FDA, proving their safety and effectiveness, before they can be sold and given to patients.

Bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cells (BM-MSCs) for the treatment of osteoarthritis.

Centeno et al. (2008) collected autologous iliac crest BM-MSCs, culture-expanded the cells, and injected 22.4×10^6 cells into the intra-articular region in an early case report of a single patient with osteoarthritis. The patient reported less pain at the 3-month follow-up, and an MRI showed increased cartilage and meniscus volume. It is unclear, nevertheless, whether the increase in cartilage volume is the result of genuine hyaline cartilage or fibrocartilage production, given the cartilage was not biopsied later on (9).

Six female patients with radiographic indications of knee OA were treated with $20\text{--}24 \times 10^6$ autologous culture-expanded iliac crest BM-MSCs, according to a series of cases reported by Emadedin et al. over the course of the first 12 months, they saw a considerable improvement in pain, functional outcomes, and maximum walking distance, with a peak improvement at 6 months. They also saw a marginal to minor improvement in physical exam findings, such as knee range of motion and patellar crepitus. Furthermore, on post-treatment MRI, there was a decrease in subchondral edema and an increase in cartilage thickness. In the 2015 follow-up trial, Emadedin et al. reported data on 17 patients (6 ankle, 6 knee, 5 hip) and broadened their treatment to include ankle and hip OA. Depending on the site, patients received different amounts of MSC treatment (ankle $57 \pm 47 \times 10^6$, hip $24 \pm 4 \times 10^6$, knee $55 \pm 8 \times 10^6$) [30]. Throughout the 30-month follow-up period, the authors observed a significant improvement in walking distance, the overall WOMAC score, and the WOMAC subscores (10).

In a pilot trial, $40 \pm 1 \times 10^6$ autologous BM-MSCs were used to treat 12 patients with radiographic indications of OA and chronic knee pain. For a full year following injection, they demonstrated a statistically significant and noteworthy improvement in pain score (11). Furthermore, during the same period following the start of treatment, they saw improvement in the mean bad cartilage index (from 19.5 to 15.4%) as determined by T2 MRI mapping, suggesting the possibility of cartilage healing. The pain score stabilized at its 12-month level in the same cohort's following 24-month follow-up research, according to Orozco et al. (12). Meanwhile, the radiographic improvement indicated by the bad cartilage index on T2 MRI mapping persisted.

A randomized controlled experiment including 30 patients was later reported by the same group (13), which compared intra-articular hyaluronic acid with allogeneic BM-MSCs. Either 40×10^6 allogeneic BM-MSCs or an equivalent volume of hyaluronic acid were injected into the patients. During the 12-month follow-up period, they saw a considerable improvement in pain and function, which was also much better than the active control that received hyaluronic acid treatment. The allogeneic MSC-treated group showed a statistically significant improvement in their mean bad cartilage index.

Application of Bone Marrow-Derived Mesenchymal Stem Cells for Focal Cartilage Defects

Using autologous culture-expanded BM-MSCs (1.3×10^7 cells per patient on average) in collagen gel, Wakitani

et al. treated localized cartilage defects in patients undergoing high tibial osteotomies by transplanting the cells into the articular cartilage lesions (14). This was an early investigation of the use of BM-MSCs in this field. Patient-reported clinical results did not differ between the experimental group and the control group, which received cell-free collagen gel; however, arthroscopy and histologic investigation showed that the experimental group had improved grading and neocartilage formation. Using autologous, culture-expanded BM-MSCs implanted under either periosteal or synovial scaffolds in three patients, Wakitani et al. conducted a smaller follow-up study examining articular cartilage defects in the patellofemoral joint. All patients had an improvement in their IKDC score, and second look arthroscopy and MRI revealed evidence of neocartilage formation (15).

Using either autologous chondrocytes or autologous BM-MSCs (9.2×10^6 cells per knee on average) implanted, Nejadnik et al. compared a non-randomized cohort of 72 patients with full-thickness cartilage defects and found improved outcomes in both groups, with no significant differences between the two cohorts about functional outcomes (16). Similar to this, Haleem et al. treated full-thickness cartilage lesions in the femoral condyles by delivering autologous BM-MSCs (mean 15×10^6 cells per knee) covered with a periosteal flap using platelet-rich fibrin glue in a smaller case series (17). At the 12-month follow-up, three of the five patients had radiographic improvement, including full defect fill and restoration of femoral condyle congruity. They also noted a significant improvement in the Lysholm and updated Hospital for Special Surgery knee score.

Although the FDA mandates a BLA for BM-MSC therapy, cBMA can be used as a therapeutic intervention without going through a drawn-out regulatory process. As a result, the number of companies providing cBMA injections has increased. A heterogeneous combination of bone marrow cells, including hematopoietic cells, is present in cBMA since it does not entail the isolation of particular phenotypic markers and the proliferation of the desired cell types. cBMA is frequently mistakenly associated with MSC therapy in both direct-to-consumer advertising and the literature currently in publication. Research frequently reports using cBMA as a source of MSCs, even though data suggests that only 0.01–0.001% of the cells in cBMA are MSCs. Despite not being a substitute for BM-MSC therapy, cBMA may still be beneficial for treating orthopedic disorders (18).

In a feasibility trial, Gessmann et al. used eight patients undergoing distraction osteogenesis. They extracted autologous bone marrow aspirate, centrifuged the aspirate to create a bone marrow concentrate, and then injected the concentrate together with thrombin into the regeneration site (19). "Short in comparison with the [previously] named studies concerning post-traumatic bone defects," according to the study's mean healing rate, which did not make use of BM augmentation. However, this comparison needs to be carefully addressed because of the small sample size and the absence of a control group. Petri et al. employed a similar technique and seeded their BM concentrates onto bovine xenogenous scaffolds for five patients with lengthy bone lesions measuring between three and fourteen centimeters (20). The group treated with cBMA was able to bear weight painlessly within an average of 11.3 weeks after surgery and had higher rates of fluoride influx on PET scans (indicating a higher perfusion rate) than the group of 11 patients who received revascularized fibular transplants for similar indications, and during the study period, achieved a bone density of 75% of the contralateral healthy bone.

Additionally being researched is the use of cBMA as an adjuvant to surgery for tendon injuries. A retrospective investigation of the impact of cBMA on primary Achilles tendon repairs was presented by Stein et al. (18). The study used randomized control trials from the literature as a historical control even though it lacked a control group. After a mean follow-up of thirty months, the MSC-treated group had higher Achilles tendon Total Rupture Scores (ATRS) than the historical control group, and there had been no re-ruptures.

For femoral head osteonecrosis, Gangji et al., Tabatabaee et al., and Pepke et al. each conducted prospective randomized clinical trials (N = 24–28 hips per study) comparing decompression boosted by autologous cBMA injections vs decompression alone (21). Similar techniques were used in these investigations, whereby bone marrow aspirate from patients' iliac crests was removed, centrifuged to concentrate it, and then implanted at

the decompression site. Patients who received these injections together demonstrated improved standardized outcome scores, decreased disease progression based on Association Research Circulation Osseous staging, and improved radiologic findings. All of these improvements were statistically significant.

Singh et al. reported a cohort of 30 patients with clinically confirmed tennis elbow who received treatment with cBMA injected at the patient's location of greatest soreness to find efficacious conservative therapy for symptomatic lateral epicondylitis (22). The feasibility of this strategy was suggested by the considerable improvement observed between pre- and post-injection scores on the Patient-rated Tennis Elbow Evaluation. However, because this study lacked a control group, only restricted conclusions could be made from it.

As an alternative to surgery, cell-based therapies are currently being studied for shoulder pathologies such as glenohumeral osteoarthritis and rotator cuff injuries. In a study by Centeno et al., 115 shoulders with one of these diagnoses were given injections of cBMA together with PRP and autologous platelet lysate (23). Pre- and post-injection pain and functional outcomes were compared and both revealed a significant improvement, despite the lack of a control group in the study. An investigation on the advantages of intra-operatively injecting cBMA during shoulder arthroscopy for rotator cuff injuries was presented by Hernigou et al. (24). At a 10-year follow-up, patients treated with cBMA mended noticeably faster and had a much lower rate of re-tear than a matched control group of 45 individuals.

Osteochondral lesions of the talus are frequently painful and unresponsive to nonsurgical treatment. It has been demonstrated that autologous chondrocyte implantation is effective, but it necessitates two surgical procedures. Giannini et al. developed a one-step process that included intraoperatively harvesting iliac crest bone marrow aspirate, centrifuging the aspirate to concentrate it, and implanting the collagen matrix along with different growth factors at the defect site using ankle arthroscopy (25). This approach was designed to reduce surgical risk and expense. Based on the American Orthopaedic Foot and Ankle Society score, patients had considerable clinical improvement at a mean evaluation time of 29 months. Additionally, MRI and histologic evaluation revealed the presence of regenerated tissue at the site of implantation. After their original findings, the study's authors published mid-term outcomes at a mean follow-up of 53 months (26).

Numerous studies assessing the effectiveness of BM-MSC treatment for musculoskeletal disorders showed statistically significant improvements in pain and functional status among the groups compared to baseline. Although this is promising, randomized controlled trials that directly compared BM-MSC with other therapeutic modalities have produced inconsistent findings. Studies that revealed no appreciable variations in outcome measures between the stem cell therapy group and the comparator group frequently focused on within-group differences or between-group subscore differences, as Jones et al. pointed out (27). Because it's feasible for readers to mistakenly believe that the changes that are highlighted are more clinically significant than the actual effect, this could deceive them.

Studies that are now available on bone marrow-derived cell therapies include a diverse range of cell processing methods, culture expansion protocols, injection volumes, concurrent surgical procedures, and combination orthobiologic therapy. Some research does not indicate the number of cells supplied; nevertheless, the studies that did report doses used a variety of delivered cell counts. According to a recent assessment, it is too difficult to determine the effectiveness of bone marrow aspirate concentrate as a treatment for orthopedic disorders due to the variability of the cell preparation techniques and the inconsistent reporting of appropriate protocols (28).

Conclusions

Mesenchymal stem cell therapy produced from bone marrow is becoming a more popular treatment for diseases and accidents related to the musculoskeletal system. Despite encouraging results from early clinical trials, methodological errors and a lack of trial standardization have restricted the inferences that can be made from the body of current research. The effectiveness and usefulness of BM-MSCs as a therapy option for different

orthopedic disorders will become clearer with a deeper comprehension of the underlying mechanism of action and more meticulously planned clinical trials.

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Contributions

Research concept and design: **CA**

Data analysis and interpretation: **CA**

Collection and/or assembly of data: **CA**

Writing the article: **CA**

Critical revision of the article: **CA**

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